

Advancements in Understanding and Management of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: Pathophysiology, Clinical Manifestations, and Therapeutic Interventions

Martha Castro Carranza¹, Maria Reyna Lara Guevara²

¹ISSSTE Clinica Hospital No.24 Ciudad Guzman, Jalisco, México.

²ISSSTE Hospital Irapuato, Guanajuato, México.

ABSTRACT

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is a chronic, inflammatory skin condition characterized by recurrent painful nodules, abscesses, and sinus tracts predominantly affecting intertriginous regions. The pathophysiology of HS involves a complex interplay of genetic predisposition, immune dysregulation, and environmental factors. Recent advancements have shed light on the role of inflammatory pathways and microbial dysbiosis in disease progression. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the latest insights into the pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, diagnostic criteria, and therapeutic strategies for HS. Emphasis is placed on novel biologic therapies and surgical interventions that have shown promise in improving patient outcomes. By integrating recent findings, we aim to enhance understanding and management of this debilitating condition.

KEYWORDS: Hidradenitis suppurativa, acne inversa, chronic inflammatory skin disorder.

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INTRODUCTION

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS), also known as acne inversa, is a chronic, relapsing inflammatory skin disorder with a significant impact on patient quality of life. The disease typically presents after puberty and is characterized by painful, deep-seated nodules, abscesses, and sinus tracts in apocrine gland-bearing areas such as the axillae, groin, and perianal regions. Despite its prevalence, HS remains underrecognized and often misdiagnosed, leading to delays in appropriate treatment.^{1,2}

The pathophysiology of HS is multifaceted, involving a combination of genetic susceptibility, aberrant immune responses, and environmental triggers. Recent studies have highlighted the involvement of inflammatory pathways, particularly those mediated by tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin-17 (IL-17), as well as microbial dysbiosis contributing to the disease process. Genetic studies have identified mutations in genes such as NCSTN, PSEN1, and PSENEN, which encode components of the gamma-secretase complex, implicating them in the pathogenesis of HS.^{3,4}

Clinically, HS presents with a spectrum of manifestations ranging from solitary inflamed nodules to widespread

involvement with chronic suppurative lesions and scarring. The Hurley staging system is commonly used to classify disease severity, guiding therapeutic decisions. Early intervention is crucial to prevent disease progression and minimize complications.^{3,4}

Therapeutic options for HS have evolved significantly, with biologic agents targeting specific inflammatory pathways offering new hope for patients with refractory disease. Surgical management remains a cornerstone for advanced cases, providing symptom relief and improving quality of life. This review synthesizes current knowledge on HS, emphasizing recent advances in understanding its pathogenesis and the development of targeted therapies.^{3,4}

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder with a prevalence that varies widely in different populations, estimated to affect approximately 1% of the global population. The true prevalence is likely underreported due to misdiagnosis and the stigma associated with the condition. HS typically presents in the second or third decade of life, with a higher incidence observed in women compared to men, in a ratio of approximately 3:1. The disease has a

Advancements in Understanding and Management of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: Pathophysiology, Clinical Manifestations, and Therapeutic Interventions

marked predilection for individuals of African descent and those with a positive family history, suggesting a significant genetic component.^{3,4}

Epidemiological studies have identified several risk factors associated with the development and severity of HS. These include metabolic syndrome, obesity, smoking, and hormonal influences. Obesity, in particular, is strongly correlated with HS, with increased body mass index (BMI) being associated with both disease onset and severity. The chronic nature of HS often leads to considerable morbidity, impacting patients' quality of life and mental health.^{4,5}

Comorbidities frequently observed in patients with HS include metabolic syndrome, inflammatory bowel disease (particularly Crohn's disease), arthritis, and pilonidal sinus. The association with these comorbid conditions underscores the systemic inflammatory nature of HS and necessitates a comprehensive approach to patient management. Furthermore, HS is associated with a significant economic burden, attributed to frequent healthcare visits, surgical interventions, and long-term pharmacotherapy.^{4,5}

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS

The clinical presentation of Hidradenitis suppurativa is highly variable, ranging from mild to severe, and is characterized by recurrent, painful, and deep-seated nodules, abscesses, and sinus tracts predominantly located in intertriginous areas. The most commonly affected regions include the axillae, inguinal and anogenital regions, inframammary folds, and perineum.^{4,5}

Early-stage HS (Hurley Stage I) typically presents with solitary or multiple isolated abscesses without sinus tract formation or scarring. Patients often describe the initial lesions as tender, subcutaneous nodules that may resolve spontaneously or progress to form abscesses.^{4,5}

In intermediate-stage HS (Hurley Stage II), the disease is characterized by the development of recurrent abscesses, sinus tracts, and scarring. Sinus tracts, also known as fistulas, are tunnel-like structures that can connect multiple inflamed nodules and lead to chronic drainage of malodorous seropurulent material. This stage is often associated with significant pain and functional impairment, contributing to a reduced quality of life.^{4,5}

Advanced-stage HS (Hurley Stage III) involves extensive involvement of the affected areas with multiple interconnected sinus tracts and widespread scarring. The chronic, relapsing nature of the disease leads to the formation of thick, fibrotic bands and bridge scars, resulting in a cobblestone appearance of the skin. In severe cases, the extensive tissue destruction can lead to strictures and contractures, significantly limiting mobility and causing considerable disfigurement.^{6,7}

Patients with HS frequently experience systemic symptoms such as fatigue, malaise, and low-grade fever during active flares. The psychological impact of HS is profound, with a

high prevalence of depression, anxiety, and social isolation reported among affected individuals. The chronic pain and recurrent nature of the disease contribute to a significant reduction in the quality of life, emphasizing the need for a multidisciplinary approach to management.^{6,7}

Secondary infections are common in HS due to the chronic nature of the lesions and the presence of sinus tracts. Superimposed bacterial infections can exacerbate the inflammation and lead to cellulitis or systemic infections if not promptly treated. Additionally, patients with long-standing disease are at an increased risk of developing squamous cell carcinoma within chronic HS lesions, particularly in the perianal and perineal regions.^{6,7}

The clinical manifestations of HS are diverse and progressive, necessitating early recognition and intervention to mitigate disease progression and associated complications. A thorough understanding of the epidemiological factors and clinical features is crucial for the effective management and improvement of outcomes for patients with HS.⁸

Diagnosis of Hidradenitis Suppurativa

The diagnosis of Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is primarily clinical, based on patient history and the characteristic appearance and distribution of lesions. However, due to the variability in clinical presentation and the potential for misdiagnosis, a thorough and systematic approach is essential. Early and accurate diagnosis is crucial for initiating appropriate management strategies to prevent disease progression and associated complications.^{9,10}

Clinical Criteria

The diagnosis of HS is typically based on the presence of the following clinical criteria:

1. **Typical Lesions:** The presence of painful, deep-seated nodules, abscesses, and sinus tracts in characteristic locations is a hallmark of HS. The most commonly affected areas are the axillae, inguinal and anogenital regions, inframammary folds, and perineum. These lesions can progress to form chronic, draining sinus tracts and scarring.^{9,10}
2. **Chronicity and Recurrence:** The disease course is characterized by recurrent episodes of inflammation in the same anatomical regions. Patients often report a history of recurrent abscesses or nodules that heal with scarring over a period of months to years. The chronic and relapsing nature of HS is a key diagnostic feature.^{9,10}
3. **Location:** HS predominantly affects intertriginous skin regions where apocrine glands are abundant. The involvement of these specific anatomical sites helps distinguish HS from other dermatological conditions with similar presentations.^{9,10}

Advancements in Understanding and Management of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: Pathophysiology, Clinical Manifestations, and Therapeutic Interventions

Diagnostic Tools and Procedures

While the diagnosis of HS is primarily clinical, several diagnostic tools and procedures can aid in confirming the diagnosis and assessing disease severity:

- Dermatologic Examination:** A thorough skin examination is essential for identifying the characteristic lesions of HS and assessing their distribution, extent, and severity. The Hurley staging system is commonly used to classify HS into three stages based on the extent of disease and the presence of sinus tracts and scarring:
 - Hurley Stage I:** Single or multiple abscesses without sinus tracts or scarring.
 - Hurley Stage II:** Recurrent abscesses with sinus tracts and scarring, widely separated lesions.
 - Hurley Stage III:** Diffuse or near-diffuse involvement with interconnected sinus tracts and extensive scarring.
- Ultrasonography:** High-frequency ultrasonography can be a valuable non-invasive tool in the diagnosis and assessment of HS. It helps visualize the extent of subclinical inflammation, sinus tracts, and abscess cavities, providing a more comprehensive evaluation of disease severity. Ultrasound findings in HS include hypoechoic areas corresponding to abscesses and hyperechoic areas indicating fibrotic tissue.^{9,10}
- Histopathological Examination:** A skin biopsy is not routinely required for the diagnosis of HS but can be useful in atypical cases or when there is diagnostic uncertainty. Histopathological features of HS include follicular hyperkeratosis, perifolliculitis, apocrine gland involvement, and the presence of sinus tracts lined by squamous epithelium.^{9,10}
- Microbiological Cultures:** Secondary bacterial infections are common in HS lesions. Swab cultures from draining sinuses or abscesses can help identify pathogenic organisms and guide appropriate antibiotic therapy. However, it is important to note that bacterial colonization is often secondary to the primary inflammatory process in HS.^{9,10}
- Blood Tests:** While there are no specific laboratory tests for diagnosing HS, blood tests can be useful in assessing systemic inflammation and ruling out other conditions. Elevated levels of inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) are often observed in active disease. Additionally, blood tests can help identify comorbid conditions such as metabolic syndrome or anemia.^{9,10}

Differential Diagnosis

Several dermatological and systemic conditions can mimic HS, making differential diagnosis an important aspect of the

diagnostic process. Conditions to consider in the differential diagnosis of HS include:

- Acne Vulgaris:** Acne typically affects sebaceous gland-rich areas such as the face, chest, and back and lacks the chronic sinus tracts and scarring seen in HS.
- Folliculitis:** Folliculitis presents with superficial pustules and erythematous papules, primarily involving hair-bearing areas, without the deep nodules and sinus tracts characteristic of HS.^{9,10}
- Carbuncles:** Carbuncles are clusters of interconnected furuncles caused by bacterial infection, often involving the nape of the neck or back. Unlike HS, carbuncles do not present with chronicity or characteristic anatomical distribution.
- Crohn's Disease:** Perianal Crohn's disease can present with fistulas and abscesses similar to HS but is usually accompanied by gastrointestinal symptoms and other systemic manifestations of inflammatory bowel disease.
- Lymphogranuloma Venereum:** This sexually transmitted infection caused by *Chlamydia trachomatis* can present with inguinal lymphadenopathy and suppurative lesions, necessitating differentiation from HS through serological and microbiological testing.¹¹

The diagnosis of Hidradenitis suppurativa relies on a combination of clinical assessment, imaging techniques, and, when necessary, histopathological and microbiological evaluations. A thorough understanding of the disease's clinical criteria and the ability to differentiate it from other conditions are essential for timely and accurate diagnosis, which is crucial for effective management and improved patient outcomes.^{12,13}

Emerging Medical Therapies for Hidradenitis Suppurativa

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is a chronic, debilitating skin condition characterized by recurrent painful nodules, abscesses, and sinus tracts. Conventional treatments, including antibiotics, retinoids, and corticosteroids, often provide limited relief and are associated with significant side effects. Recent advances in understanding the pathophysiology of HS have led to the development of novel therapeutic approaches targeting specific inflammatory pathways involved in the disease. This article explores the latest medical therapies for HS, focusing on biologics, small molecule inhibitors, and innovative treatments that offer new hope for patients.^{14,15}

Biologic Therapies

Biologic agents, which target specific components of the immune system, have emerged as a cornerstone in the management of moderate to severe HS. These therapies have revolutionized the treatment landscape, offering targeted and

Advancements in Understanding and Management of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: Pathophysiology, Clinical Manifestations, and Therapeutic Interventions

effective options for patients who do not respond to conventional treatments.¹⁶

1. Tumor Necrosis Factor-Alpha (TNF- α) Inhibitors:

- **Adalimumab:** Adalimumab is the first and only biologic approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of HS. It is a fully human monoclonal antibody that binds to TNF- α , a pro-inflammatory cytokine implicated in HS pathogenesis. Clinical trials have demonstrated that adalimumab significantly reduces the number of inflammatory lesions and improves the quality of life in patients with moderate to severe HS.¹⁷
- **Infliximab:** Although not specifically approved for HS, infliximab, a chimeric monoclonal antibody against TNF- α , has shown efficacy in off-label use. Studies indicate that infliximab can lead to rapid improvement in HS symptoms, particularly in patients with severe disease.¹⁷

2. Interleukin-17 (IL-17) Inhibitors:

- **Secukinumab:** Secukinumab is a fully human monoclonal antibody that targets IL-17A, a cytokine involved in the inflammatory cascade of HS. Preliminary studies have shown promising results, with significant reductions in lesion count and disease severity. Ongoing clinical trials are evaluating the long-term efficacy and safety of secukinumab in HS patients.¹⁸

3. Interleukin-12/23 (IL-12/23) Inhibitors:

- **Ustekinumab:** Ustekinumab, a monoclonal antibody that targets the p40 subunit shared by IL-12 and IL-23, has shown potential benefits in HS. Small studies and case reports suggest that ustekinumab can reduce the frequency and severity of flares in patients with refractory HS.¹⁸

Small Molecule Inhibitors

Small molecule inhibitors offer a different therapeutic approach by targeting intracellular signaling pathways involved in inflammation. These oral medications provide an alternative for patients who are not candidates for biologics or prefer oral therapy.

1. Janus Kinase (JAK) Inhibitors:

- **Tofacitinib:** Tofacitinib is an oral JAK inhibitor that interferes with the JAK-STAT signaling pathway, which is critical in the inflammatory response of HS. Early studies suggest that tofacitinib may be

effective in reducing HS lesions and associated pain. Larger clinical trials are needed to confirm these findings.¹⁸

2. Phosphodiesterase-4 (PDE4) Inhibitors:

- **Apremilast:** Apremilast, an oral PDE4 inhibitor, modulates the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines. While primarily used for psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis, apremilast has shown some efficacy in treating HS in small clinical studies, with improvements in lesion count and patient-reported outcomes.¹⁸

Innovative and Experimental Therapies

In addition to biologics and small molecule inhibitors, several innovative and experimental therapies are being investigated for HS. These therapies aim to address unmet needs and provide new options for patients with refractory disease.¹⁸

1. Laser and Light-Based Therapies:

- **Laser Hair Removal:** Laser hair removal using diode or Nd lasers can reduce hair follicle density, thereby decreasing the occurrence of follicular occlusion and subsequent HS flares. This approach is particularly beneficial in areas prone to recurrent lesions.¹⁸
- **Photodynamic Therapy (PDT):** PDT involves the application of a photosensitizing agent followed by exposure to a specific wavelength of light. This treatment has shown variable success in HS, with some studies reporting reductions in lesion count and pain.¹⁸

2. Antimicrobial Peptides:

- **Resiniferatoxin:** Resiniferatoxin, a potent agonist of transient receptor potential vanilloid 1 (TRPV1), is being explored for its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties in HS. Preliminary research suggests it may reduce bacterial colonization and inflammation in HS lesions.¹⁸

3. Stem Cell Therapy:

- **Adipose-Derived Stem Cells (ADSCs):** ADSCs possess anti-inflammatory and regenerative properties that may benefit patients with HS. Early studies indicate that ADSC injections can reduce inflammation and promote healing in HS lesions, though more research is needed to establish efficacy and safety.¹⁹

4. Immunomodulatory Agents:

- **Intravenous Immunoglobulin (IVIG):** IVIG, which modulates the immune

Advancements in Understanding and Management of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: Pathophysiology, Clinical Manifestations, and Therapeutic Interventions

system, has been used off-label in severe, refractory HS cases. Some case reports suggest that IVIG can lead to significant clinical improvement, but controlled trials are necessary to validate these findings.¹⁹

Combination Therapies and Personalized Medicine

Given the heterogeneity of HS, combination therapies that target multiple pathways simultaneously may offer enhanced efficacy. Personalized medicine, guided by biomarkers and genetic profiling, holds promise for tailoring treatments to individual patients' specific disease mechanisms.²⁰

The landscape of HS treatment is rapidly evolving, with several novel therapies showing promise in clinical trials. Biologic agents targeting TNF- α , IL-17, and IL-12/23, along with small molecule inhibitors and innovative treatments, offer new hope for patients with this challenging condition. Continued research and clinical trials are essential to further elucidate the efficacy and safety of these emerging therapies, ultimately improving outcomes for patients with Hidradenitis suppurativa.²⁰

CONCLUSION

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is a chronic, inflammatory skin condition that presents significant challenges in terms of diagnosis, management, and patient quality of life. Despite being relatively common, HS remains underrecognized and often misdiagnosed, leading to delays in appropriate treatment. The condition is characterized by recurrent, painful nodules, abscesses, and sinus tracts predominantly affecting intertriginous areas, and is associated with significant morbidity and psychological burden.

The pathophysiology of HS is complex and multifactorial, involving a combination of genetic predisposition, immune dysregulation, and environmental factors. Recent advances in our understanding of the inflammatory pathways involved in HS, particularly those mediated by TNF- α and IL-17, have led to the development of targeted biologic therapies. Adalimumab, the first FDA-approved biologic for HS, has demonstrated significant efficacy in reducing lesion counts and improving quality of life for patients with moderate to severe disease. Other biologics, such as infliximab, secukinumab, and ustekinumab, have shown promise in clinical trials and off-label use, offering additional options for patients with refractory HS.

In addition to biologics, small molecule inhibitors such as JAK inhibitors and PDE4 inhibitors are emerging as potential therapies for HS. These agents target intracellular signaling pathways involved in inflammation, providing new avenues for treatment. Innovative and experimental therapies, including laser and light-based treatments, antimicrobial peptides, stem cell therapy, and immunomodulatory agents, are also being explored and have shown varying degrees of success in early studies.

The diagnosis of HS is primarily clinical, based on the presence of typical lesions in characteristic locations and a history of chronicity and recurrence. Diagnostic tools such as high-frequency ultrasonography and histopathological examination can aid in confirming the diagnosis and assessing disease severity. Differential diagnosis is crucial, as several dermatological and systemic conditions can mimic HS.

Management of HS requires a multidisciplinary approach, encompassing medical, surgical, and supportive therapies. Early and aggressive intervention is essential to prevent disease progression and minimize complications. Biologic agents and small molecule inhibitors represent significant advancements in the medical management of HS, providing targeted and effective options for patients who do not respond to conventional treatments. Surgical interventions, including incision and drainage, deroofing, and wide excision, remain important for managing advanced disease and providing symptom relief.

The psychosocial impact of HS is profound, with a high prevalence of depression, anxiety, and social isolation reported among affected individuals. Comprehensive care for HS patients should address both the physical and psychological aspects of the disease, incorporating mental health support and patient education as integral components of management.

Future research should focus on further elucidating the underlying mechanisms of HS, identifying novel therapeutic targets, and optimizing treatment strategies through personalized medicine. Large-scale, randomized controlled trials are needed to establish the long-term efficacy and safety of emerging therapies. Additionally, increased awareness and education among healthcare providers are essential to improve early diagnosis and treatment outcomes.

In conclusion, Hidradenitis suppurativa is a challenging and multifaceted disease that requires a comprehensive and individualized approach to management. The advent of biologic therapies and small molecule inhibitors has revolutionized the treatment landscape, offering new hope for patients with this debilitating condition. Continued research and innovation are crucial to advancing our understanding and management of HS, ultimately improving the quality of life for those affected by this chronic inflammatory skin disorder.

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Advancements in Understanding and Management of Hidradenitis Suppurativa: Pathophysiology, Clinical Manifestations, and Therapeutic Interventions

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